

Relationship of Primary Nurses Service with Satisfaction of Patients of Road Poli Care in Kudungga District of Eastern Kutai

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ABSTRACT

Patient satisfaction rate data on primary poli street care services in RSUD Kudungga 2023 has not been re-enquired by the hospital. The study aims to explain the relationship between primary nurses' services and the satisfaction rate of road polio patients in Kudungga district of Eastern Kutai district in 2023. Type of quantitative research with analytical studies and using cross sectional designs. The sample was 186 people using purposive sampling. The instrument used is a questionnaire. The data was then analyzed univariately and bivariately with the Chi Square test. The results of the research showed that there was a relationship between primary nursing services and the satisfaction rate of the patients of the RSUD Kudungga medical clinic.

INTRODUCTION

As part of the health system, hospitals provide a wide range of health services to the community, including nursing, medical support, medical rehabilitation and nurse services. Hospitals are one of the chain points in the reference of health care that has a strategic role in increasing public participation and is judged to be able to provide the best service because hospitals have a lot of human or professional resources, more advanced technology and a more comprehensive household management system. (Arifin, Umar, Yunus 2022).

According to the Ministry of Health Regulation No. 66/Menkes/II/2005 Road care services are hospital and street care services offered to the public who come to the hospital for observation, diagnosis, treatment, rehabilitation and other health needs, where the functional application unit of road care treatment is general and specialized poliklinics and emergency (Sinulingga, et al 2021).

In the law No. 36 of 2009 on health, it says that the government is obliged to organize the fulfilment of the basic right of public health protection in improving the health status through health care institutions. (Bahar, 2019).

Excellent service is the best service provided by hospital officers to meet even exceed the expectations of hospital service users (Mohamad, et al 2022) Service Excellence is a high-quality service and always constantly and accurately monitors the development of client needs at all times. Oriented to customer satisfaction, always aware of developments in international standards/ISO and implementing comprehensive quality management and high quality awareness (Rohayani, dkk 2020).

Premium service is offered to everyone, especially customers with good behavior and attitude. Premium service isn't just about customer satisfaction and attention, but also about how to respond to customer requests in a way that can leave a positive impression on customers. (Mohammad, et al 2022). In the journal (Umar, Yunus and Blongkod, 2022) where the results of this study were respondents who rated primary service of primary category as many as (45,5%) respondents, the category is quite primary as much as (54.5%) respondents. The results showed that there is a link between primary service and the level of patient satisfaction in the hospital room of RSUD intern Dr. Hasri Ainun Habibie Province of Gorontalo The good hospital service proves that the hospital is of high quality. One of the indicators of hospital health care success is patient satisfaction. Satisfaction is a function of the impression of performance and expectation, in which the patient is only satisfied when the outcome of the health care provided to him meets or exceeds his expectations, and instead the patient feels dissatisfied or disappointed when the performance of health care received does not meet his expectation. (Mega, Nadapdap, Jamaluddin 2020). This is in line with the journal (Rina, 2021) where the results show that primary service is measured using six indicators: attitude, attention, action, ability, appearance, and responsibility. (accountability). Studies show that primary care affects patient satisfaction in hospitals.

Patient satisfaction is the level of a person's feelings after comparing the performance of a product or results that the patient feels with his expectations. With consumers feeling satisfied with a long-term use, because consumer satisfaction will affect actions based on past experience where they will not be able to transfer services because of marketing stimulus (Minaria, Sitorus 2021). The results of the study showed (57.1%) patients said they were unsatisfied, (62.9%) said the quality of the service was poor. There is a meaningful relationship between the quality of service and patient satisfaction.

Nursalam, (2015) explains that to get a picture of customer satisfaction, it can be done with a service quality approach measured using indicators of physical evidence (tangibles), reliability (reliability), responsiveness (responsiveness), assurance (assurance), and empathy. (empathy).

Patient satisfaction is one of the indicators of the quality of service that we provide and patient satisfaction was a capital to get more patients and to get loyal patients. (Nursalam, 2014). So when the service given to the patient in the hospital meets expectations even exceeds the expectations of the patient called with primary service, then gives satisfaction to the patients. Satisfied patients facilitate the process of healing in the patient so that the primary purpose of the service to be able to provide healing (Pratiwi, Putra 2021). In the journal (Ginting, Ginting 2021) where the results of the study show that there is a significant relationship between the quality of service and the satisfaction of class 1 hospitalized patients where tangible $p(0,038) < \alpha(0,05)$, reliability $p(0,003) < \alpha(0,05)$, responsiveness $(0,026) < (0,05)$, assurance $p(0,002) < \alpha(0,05)$ and empathy $p(0,0005) < \alpha(0,05)$. It is hoped for the health care personnel to improve the quality of the services provided especially in the first class nursing room, clean the rooms, apply smiles, greetings, speed, can provide primary service and accuracy in the schedule of patient examination so that the relationship between the patient and the nurse is created.

Based on the results of the preliminary study conducted by the researchers at RSUD Kudungga on December 2, 2022 obtained data of the total percentage of the level of satisfaction of road care customers overall in RSUD kudungga in 2021, which is where 0.01% of patients declared very dissatisfied, 2.64% of patients said not satisfied, 86.32% of the patients said satisfied and 11.03% of the patient said very satisfied with the road care services.

Based on the above conditions, the author would like to prove the relationship between primary nursing services and the satisfaction rate of patients in the medical clinic of Kudungga district of Eastern Kutai in 2023.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

Primary Service

Primary service is a translation of the term "excellent service" which literally means the best service or excellent service. It is called very good or best because it is in accordance with the standards of service applicable or owned by the service provider agencies (Mukarom Zaenal and Wijaya Laksana, 2018).

According to Rahmayanty (2010) primary services are:

- 1) Excellent service that exceeds customer expectations.
- 2) Service that has quality nice.

- 3) Service with a high standard of quality and always follow the evolution of customer needs at all times, consistently and accurately.

METHODOLOGY

Type of quantitative research with analytical studies and using cross sectional designs. The sample was 186 people using purposive sampling. The research was carried out in January until March 2023 at RSUD Kudungga Road Police. The instrument used is a questionnaire that has been tested for validity and feasibility.

The data obtained will be processed and the results will be displayed as a percentage of the frequency distribution table using the univariate analysis formula. The data is then processed with the help of computerization using statistical tests. Where the bi-variation test in this study uses a chi square with a fertility limit of $\alpha=0,05$.

RESULTS

Univariat Analysis

Table 1. Characteristics of Respondents in Road Care Installation RSUD Kudungga Year 2023

	Karakteristik	Persentase (%)
Jenis Kelamin	Laki-laki	44.1
	Perempuan	55.9
	Total	100.0
Usia	15 - 30 Tahun	28.5
	31-50 Tahun	53.2
	≥ 51 Tahun	18.3
	Total	100.0
Pendidikan	Tidak Bersekolah	2.7
	SD	7.5
	SMP	11.8
	SMA	44.1
	PT/ Perguruan Tinggi	33.9
	Total	100.0
Pekerjaan	PNS	11.3
	Swasta	40.3
	Wiraswasta	12.4
	Lain-lain	36.0
	Total	100.0

Table 1 above shows that respondents based on the gender group are mostly female respondents 55.9 % and a small proportion are male respondents 44.1 %. Based on table 1 above, respondents according to the age group are mainly aged between 31-50 years 53.2 %, a minor proportion of respondents aged 15-30 years 28.5 % and very few are aged ≥ 51 years 18.3 %.

Based on table 1 above shows that respondents based on educational groups almost half respondents with high school education 44.1% and very few not attending school 2.7%. Based upon table 1 below shows that responders based on job groups half private respondents 40.3% and very little PNS 11.3%.

Table 2. Frequency of respondents based on primary service in RSUD Kudungga road care facilities in 2023

Pelayanan Prima	Frekuensi	Persentase (%)
Tidak Baik	17	9.1
Cukup Baik	135	72.6
Baik	34	18.3
Total	186	100.0

The table 2 above shows that based on the primary service respondent group, the majority of respondents said 135 people (72.6 per cent), a small proportion said 34 people (18.3 per cent) and very few respondents say 17 people (9.1 per cent).

Table 3. Frequency of Respondents Based on Patient Satisfaction in RSUD Kudungga Road Care Facilities 2023

Kepuasan Pasien	Frekuensi	Persentase (%)
Puas	103	55.4
Tidak Puas	83	44.6
Total	186	100.0

Based on table 3 above shows that based on the patient satisfaction group, the majority of respondents said 103 people were satisfied (55.4%) and a small proportion said 83 people were not satisfied (44.6%).

Table 4. Analysis of Bivariat Relationship of Primary Nurses Service with Satisfaction Rate of Patients of Jalandi Police Care RSUD Kudungga District of Eastern Kutai Year 2023

	Kepuasan Pasien				Total	Pvalue
	Puas		Tidak Puas			
Pelayanan Prima	Tidak Baik	2	1.1 %	15	8.1 %	0.000
	Cukup Baik	78	41.9 %	57	30.6 %	
	Baik	23	12.4%	11	5.9%	
Total	103	55.4%	83	44.6%	186	100.0%

*Uji Chi-square

Based on the results of the bivariate analysis in table 4 above, the result was that in the primary service variable not good with patient satisfaction category there were 2 people out of 186 respondents (1.1%) and the category not satisfied there were 15 people out Of 186 respondents (8.1%). In the Primary Service variable C quite good with the satisfaction of the patient category satisfied as many as 78 persons out of 186 respondents (41.9%) and who got the prima service quite well with the contentment of the patients category not satisfaction as much as 57 persons Out of 186 responders (30.6%). And in the

variable of the good service with satisfaction patient category so much as 23 people Out of 186, respondents (12.4%) and those who get the prime service well with contentment patient category unsatisfied so many as 11 people Out Of 186 replies (5.9%).

The statistical analysis of the Chi-square trial table 3x2 showed Pvalue is 0,000 where it is less than the P-value value 0.05 which means H0 rejected so it can be concluded that there is a relationship between primary nursing service and the satisfaction rate of the patient.

DISCUSSION

This study is in line with the results of Silvia study (2018) known significant value of primary service of $0,000 < \text{probability value of } 0.05$ which means that H0 was rejected and H1 was accepted so it can be concluded that there is a significant influence of the primary services variable on customer satisfaction. Along with the study of Kelana, M T (2015) also concludes that the value of $p (0.000) < 0.05$ meaning H0 is refused and depending on the application of the first service (service excellence) of nurses is rated satisfaction of the patient at the University Hospital of TanjungpuraPontianak.

The results of this study are in line with the theory proposed by Barata (2003) that primary service involves a careful attitude that can satisfy needs and realize customer satisfaction.

Good primary service will have a positive impact on the satisfaction the patient feels. A study conducted by Ariyani and Rosinta (2010) supports the findings. Their results indicate that the quality of service has a positive impact on patient satisfaction. A good perception of the quality of the service received and a good hospital image, the greater the patient's expectations are fulfilled and the more satisfied the patient is.

Syamsiah (2011) states that the link between quality of service and perceived value is that quality service will increase value for customers so that it can create satisfaction that can ultimately increase customer loyalty.

One of the important aspects of primary service is the aspect of appearance or physical evidence. Nurses are required to provide the best possible appearance in providing services to patients so that they can generate a high level of satisfaction. (Nasution, 2009). This is demonstrated by Zarei, et.al (2012) in his research that the results of physical evidence aspects (clean appearance of nurses, clean and comfortable environment, modern equipment) have a higher influence on patient satisfaction.

According to the researchers, the quality of the services provided by the hospital is satisfactory to the patient. The satisfaction felt by the quality of the service received, the greater the patient's desire to be faithful in using the hospital's services and willing to recommend it to others. Patient satisfaction tends to be unstable because the measurement of patient satisfaction with service is essentially a subjective and dynamic result. However, the best way to do it is to make the differences happen as an input to the hospital and to take advantage of the phenomenon so as to obtain the best solution and be based on the prime service provided.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the explanation and description, it can be concluded that Primary Service in RSUD Road Care Facilities I am the majority of respondents say getting primary services good enough of 135 people (72.6%), a small proportion say getting prime services good of 34 people (18.3%) and very few respondents said primary service not good of 17 people (9.1%). In this study it can be concluded that there is a relationship between primary service and the level of satisfaction of patients with poly care under RSUD Kudungga.

The percentage of respondents who are “satisfied” with hospital services is not expected to satisfy quickly because there are still many services that need to be improved so that hospital services are closer to the needs and wishes of patients. These patient satisfaction indicators can help managers to carry out repairs to improve service performance and patient contentment. This requires a continuous and programmed effort from the entire hospital line to improve the management of services.

FURTHER STUDY

It is hoped that further researchers will be able to conduct qualitative research to deepen the factors that cause dissatisfaction from various points of view so that before the research begins, they have identified various sources that may cause bias and planned efforts to prevent the occurrence of errors.

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